

A Study on Success Motivation and Academic Engagement of Teenage Students Suffering from Test Anxiety

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to study success motivation and academic engagement of teenage students suffering from test anxiety. Quantitative methods will be employed in his investigation, and broad research questions will be posed. Systematic random selection will be used to choose participants, and questionnaires will be used to collect data for the study. A sample of 500 young individuals who are now enrolled in educational institutions will be used as responders. The collected data will be analyzed using SPSS, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences.

1. Introduction

Those who suffer from test anxiety are afflicted with a psychological ailment that causes them considerable nervousness and worry whenever they are put in a testing environment. Exam worry can genuinely hinder learning and damage test performance, despite the fact that many people experience some degree of stress and anxiety before and during tests [7].

Students all across the world experience test anxiety, a debilitating affliction that can hinder their academic achievement and overall well-being. The study's findings suggest that test anxiety can be detrimental in any setting when individuals of any age or social status are being judged or ranked on the basis of their skills, accomplishments, or areas of interest [8]-[10].

2. Literature Survey

This investigation will learn how significant the test is, how challenging the material is, and how well students are prepared for it. Exam anxiety is a psychological syndrome that can negatively impact people in many walks of life, but particularly students taking standardised tests [11]. Anxiety levels rise in response to a subject's perceived difficulty. Cognitive therapy and other types of psychological intervention are predicted to alleviate students' test anxiety and other forms of psychological discomfort, leading to better academic outcomes [12].

3. Problem Statement

Worrying over exams is now being recognised as a kind of social anxiety. Those who suffer from social phobias have an extreme and irrational dread of any circumstance where they might feel humiliated in front of other people. A person has to exhibit all four of these symptoms in order to be diagnosed with social phobia [3]-[4]

This research need to demonstrate instant worry when put in the dreaded social or performance circumstance.

It demonstrate a range of strategies for avoiding or getting through performance or social situations in which you feel uncomfortable.

A person's typical routine must be affected by their anxiety or fear of this event.

- You need to have had the condition for at least six months.

Exam stress can also be influenced by a number of other factors, including:

- An obsession with perfection and a need to always achieve unattainable goals [5].

4. Framework

Students who are able to manage their stress and anxiety effectively have a healthy lifestyle. They should have a good sleep schedule and eat well. Those who suffer from test anxiety are more prone to having negative thoughts when being evaluated, as stated by the research of Baddeley, Alan (2013). Anxious test takers are also more likely to pay attention to signs that evoke negative emotions, such as those linked with threats [2].

4.1. Research design

This investigation into the factors that contribute to exam anxiety and performance among middle and high school students is mostly descriptive in nature. A fact-finding inquiry that incorporates appropriate interpretation forms the foundation for the descriptive research design. It zeroed in on a single aspect or component of the topic that was being researched. Because it focuses directly on the theoretical elements and highlights the more significant methodological features of data gathering in an area of directed study, descriptive research was chosen by the research as the technique of investigation [6].

4.2. Research population and sample

Adolescent students in the middle and high schools who are enrolled in the eighth through twelfth grades (that is, students who are between the ages of 13 and 18) make up the study's population. In this study, the researchers use a method called convenient sampling, where the sample is taken from a group of people who are easy to contact or to reach. The researcher had collected data from 27 different schools, which accounted for 25% of the total. In these 27 schools, the responses range in age from 13 to 18 years old, this corresponds to the eighth to twelfth grade levels. There are now 5022 pupils in this age bracket that are attending school. The sample size that had been employed in this research was 500 students, which constituted 10% of the total.

Table 4.1. Exam anxiety and Academic Performance

S.No.	Statements	Average Mean	Interpretation
1.	My Exam performance improved due to Anxiety on exam.	3.41	Agree
2.	The more difficult the examination, the less efficient I become.	3.11	Neutral
3.	While taking a test, I feel confident and relaxed.	3.57	Agree
4.	During exams, If I find myself thinking of things unrelated to the course material.	2.86	Neutral

5.	I feel under a lot of pressure to get good grades on tests.	3.52	Agree
6.	I feel difficulty in choosing questions to answer.	2.80	Neutral
7.	When I take a test, my nervousness causes me to make careless errors.	3.48	Agree
8.	When I have to take a difficult course, I am worried about test.	3.44	Agree
9.	Finding unexpected questions on a test causes me to feel challenged rather than panicky.	2.94	Neutral
10.	I am worried if my classmates get marks better than me.	2.28	Disagree
11.	I think that anxiety facilitates my learning.	3.52	Agree
12.	When taking an exam I won't let my disturbing feelings to obstruct with my performance.	4.01	Agree
13.	I receive regular motivation from the school regarding my academic performance.	3.30	Neutral
14.	My teachers handling learning issues well	3.90	Agree
15.	I take additional coaching which helps to improve my exam performance.	4.37	Strongly Agree

4.3. Suggestions

- ✓ In order to alleviate their pupils' anxiety about the upcoming examinations, teachers should provide helpful information.
- ✓ Students can increase their performance on exams by increasing their level of worry. Therefore, kids need to understand that the worrying is beneficial.
- ✓ Before beginning to write the test, the students should make sure that their minds are clear of concerns and that they are prepared.
- ✓ Parents shouldn't bring up issues that are going on in the family while their children have tests coming up.
- ✓ The school ought to provide additional mentoring opportunities for pupils who are struggling academically.
- ✓ Students need to be aware that the pressure they feel during exams may help them develop discipline, strengthen their memory, and make them more competitive.

5. Research Summary and Conclusions

This research provides conclusive evidence that everyone suffers from anxiety. Despite the fact that the vast majority of students use worry to their advantage, it does not increase their grades. The remaining responders'

efficiency drops because of worry. Anxiety may be put to good use if suitable counselling is provided to those students.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The author declares no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The author declares that he/she consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The author is willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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